

REMEDICATION THROUGH OOTD (ONLINE AND OFFLINE TUTORIAL DELIVERY) APPROACH: TOOL TO ENHANCE STUDENTS LEARNING PERFORMANCE IN EARTH SCIENCE AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN BAUAN TECHNICAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop strategies in providing best remediation for the students, specifically it determined the perception of parents and students on online and tutorial teaching delivery during the distance learning in Earth Science of Grade 11 students in Bauan Technical High School. Likewise, to assess the performance of the students before and after the administration of remedial education through OOTD with Individual Learning Monitoring Plan (ILMP). The respondents of the student were 150 students which was determined through Slovin's formula, the parents of these students were used also as the respondents to seek their perception on OOTD. Descriptive method of research was utilized, and the research instrument used in this study is a pre-designed questionnaire for the parents and students also pre-assessment, and post-assessment for the students. The questionnaire was used to collect data, which was used to determine the perception of parents and students on the OOTD Approach. The questionnaire was composed of questions that determined the respondents' perception on the tutorial delivery during distance learning, The questionnaire also provided some profile of the students and parents. The researcher also provided an evaluation tool to be answered by the students to determine the approach effectiveness. The pre-assessment was a multiple-choice type and was composed of 30 items. It included questions on Earth Science was based on the most essential learning competencies under K-12 Program of DepEd during pandemic. Post assessment was also a multiple-choice type of questionnaire composed of Thirty (30) items. It also contained questions on earth science that helped evaluate what they learned. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Z and T-test of correlated or paired samples compared the means between two related groups obtained from the same sample. These were utilized in testing the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the students' pre - test and post- test scores. The rejection or acceptances of the null hypotheses was based on some level of difference as a criterion, the 5% and 1% level. Based on the perspective of the students, the OOTD Approach in Earth science gives reinforcement activities and provides better opportunity and time for learning, motivates them, and corrects their behavior toward school, and can increase the level of student's performance and decrease the students' dropouts. Furthermore, based on the perspective of the parents, the OOTD Approach in Earth science gives reinforcement activities for students, is meant to improve learning skills of the students, and provides better opportunity and time for learning. The performance of the students based on the assessment were interpreted from satisfactory to very satisfactory. On the same way, the results of the student showed that there is significant different between the level of performance of students before and after Science Online and Offline Tutorial Delivery.

Keywords: Tutorial Delivery, Perception, Performance